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Low Temperature Site-Specific Pulsed Laser Annealing of MoS₂

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ABSTRACT

A precise, non-thermal, ultrashort pulsed laser process for selective and localized structural modification relevant to two-dimensional (2D) transition-metal-dichalcogenides (TMDs) ultra-thin films is reported. The approach enables site-specific pulsed laser annealing (SSPLA) and is shown to be effective in improving the electrical and structural properties of CVD-grown MoS₂ thin film devices with precision and control. High spatial overlapping of laser pulses is employed to anneal regions of MoS₂ thin films on SiO₂-Si substrates using laser fluences less than 12 mJ cm⁻² which is less than the threshold fluence for causing damage on surfaces. The process is implemented in ambient air at specific sites using laser beam scanning technology. Raman spectra confirm the conversion of amorphous to crystalline MoS₂. The application of the site-specific annealing process confirms a reduction in actual MoS₂ path resistance by up to a factor of four in devices. Cross sectional STEM confirms thinning and improvements to the degree of crystallization of partially crystallized films. AFM data indicates enlargement of isotropic grain structures with increasing fluence. The evidence suggests that crystallization occurs by local solid-state diffusion at low temperatures. The site-selective process is highly suitable for scalable precision back end of line processing in semiconductor wafer fabrication.

1 | Introduction

Molybdenum disulfide (MoS₂) is one of the most important families of transition metal dichalcogenides (TMD). In MoS₂, each monolayer consisting of molybdenum atoms, are sandwiched between two sulphur atoms and are held together by weak van der Waals forces [1]. MoS₂ exhibits three different structural phases i.e. a hexagonal (2H) phase, a trigonal (1T) phase and a rhombohedral (3R) phase, each leading to different electronic properties. The primary phase of MoS₂ is 2H which is the most thermodynamically stable for a semiconductor structure with an individual layer or that of a few monolayers. 1T is a metastable

metallic phase. 3R is a phase with some semiconductor nature [2, 3]. MoS₂ in the 2H phase exhibits a tuneable bandgap energy ranging from indirect to direct bandgap transitions (1.2 to 1.9 eV) as the size reduces from bulk to the nano-scale range. The metallic 1T phase offers higher electrical conductivity as the size reduces from bulk to the nano-scale range. The properties, like high mobility [1], tuneable bandgap [4], strong mechanical and chemical stability [5–7] makes MoS₂ an excellent candidate for electronics (transistors, integrated circuits) [8–10], optoelectronic devices (photodetectors, solar cells, LED's) [11–13], optical switching [14], energy storage (batteries and supercapacitors) [15, 16], sensors (biosensors, gas sensors) [17–21], nanotechnology and

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quantum applications (quantum dots, spintronics) [22–24] and water purification etc [25].

The next-generation flexible devices require thin films deposited at low temperatures to prevent any deformation or degradation of heat sensitive substrates and to maintain device performance. Similarly, back end of line processing of semiconductor wafers requires low temperatures. Typical annealing processes for TMDs require a high thermal budget to optimize the electrical properties for specific applications. Standard growth methods for 2D TMDs such as chemical vapor deposition (CVD) [26], molecular-beam epitaxy (MBE) [27], and atomic layer deposition (ALD) [28] are capable of high-quality growth and control over a number of atomic layers at relatively high temperatures. However, it is challenging to attain the same quality material for growth performed at lower temperatures. Hence solutions are required to implement a subsequent thermal processing step to modify electro-optical properties in localized regions of a device produced at low temperatures. The spatial precision for such thermal processing is a key consideration, as high temperature gradients can easily damage the surrounding devices or components on a chip. Therefore, it is crucial to develop a technique by lowering the processing temperatures in any site-specific localized processing of TMDs.

Femtosecond laser technologies are a promising platform offering precise and localized energy transfer to the material in a well-controlled fashion with repetition rates up to MHz. The advantages associated with this laser technology, is that it is high-speed, it has microns precision, it depends on well-controlled process parameters such as pulse duration, wavelength, and fluence range. The range of these parameters can enable many scalable processes in dicing, micromachining, nanopores fabrication, structuring, doping, surface functionalization, and crystallization [29–32].

In terms of the functionality of TMDs, the contact resistance - in part created by a Schottky barrier (SB) height - is a critical concern that restricts the charge carrier transport across the metal-semiconductor junction (MSJ) resulting in poor device performance [33]. Laser annealing can significantly reduce this contact resistance by changing the phase of the material, such as converting the semiconducting 2H phase to the metallic 1T phase at the contact region, or by improving the crystallinity, at the contact region. This reduces SB heights and enhances the charge carrier injection leading to better device performance. For example, it was demonstrated that a continuous wave (CW) 532 nm laser can be applied to the metal semiconductor junction in a vacuum environment for enhancing the carrier mobility of monolayer MoS₂ based devices by up to 20 times by reducing the contact resistance [34]. Under direct laser irradiation of MoS₂ in ambient conditions, etching and redeposition of amorphous phase of MoS₂ was observed at low laser powers, and nanoparticle generation and oxidation of MoS₂ occurred at higher fluence [35]. Similarly with 473 nm CW laser, under relatively low laser power, MoS₂ was crystallized with nanostructured and sharp ridges and valleys, while at high power MoS₂ was converted into metallic Mo by sulphur reduction in MoS₂ [36]. Kim et al. investigated the oxygen diffusion in WS₂ on an Al₂O₃ layer stacked with Ti/Au electrodes due to thermal effects during CW 532 nm laser annealing, leading to a decrease in resistance because

of an increase in the carriers' mobility. Kim et al. explained that the laser generated thermal energy dissociates Al–O bonds and released the oxygen atoms into the WS₂ layer by creating sulphur vacancies, thereby facilitating substitutional doping [37]. However, there exists some challenges associated with device performance such as careful tuning of structural and electronic properties according to device selection, implementing controlled doping, and adjusting the contact resistance of multilayers using low temperature based annealing methods to explore the full potential of TMDs based devices.

Ultrashort pulsed lasers are particularly advantageous over the CW and long-pulse sources for annealing of 2D TMDs materials and in improving the contact resistance. Processes dramatically change in laser material interactions when the pulse duration becomes ultrashort (\leq picosecond) and non-linear phenomena are enabled. Compared with longer pulse durations (millisecond to nanoseconds), ultrashort pulses are characterized by their high peak power and short pulse durations on timescales less than or equivalent to major electron-lattice relaxation processes [38]. The selection of laser parameters enables modification of ultrathin materials by electron absorption, followed by a short athermal excited electron phase for a few femtoseconds, and then a two-temperature regime when the thermalised high electron temperatures and low lattice temperatures are established for up to a few picoseconds [39]. The energy in the electron system is then fully thermalised to the lattice. Care is taken with the applied fluence to ensure that the lattice never approaches a melting point temperature. The concept underpinning this work is to restructure the MoS₂ film in the few picoseconds after the onset of the laser pulse when the electron and lattice temperatures are not in equilibrium.

We propose a site-specific pulsed laser annealing process by using a non-thermal ultrashort laser enabled process for selective modification of MoS₂ thin films without melting or generating excessive heat for nearby components on a chip. Annealed materials are characterised using Raman, cross-sectional scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM), and Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM). The electrical impact of the annealing process is characterised using a linear transfer length method (L-TLMs) and a simple 2-point resistor geometry. The proposed method for annealing is shown to be highly effective. This facile, non-melt, selective crystallization process is highly relevant for thin film processing on heat sensitive substrates.

2 | Materials and Methods

2.1 | Film Synthesis & Device Fabrication

MoS₂ thin films targeting a thickness of \sim 6.5 nm in a semiconductor phase (2H) were grown on SiO₂-Si substrates using chemical vapor deposition (CVD) at 400°C. The substrates consisted of an 85 nm thick SiO₂ layer thermally grown on a *p*-type Si wafer. The MoS₂ growth was carried out in a 300 mm reactor, utilizing Mo (CO)₆ and 1% H₂S (99.999%) in Argon (Ar) as the precursors. Prior to MoS₂ deposition, the substrates were cleaned by sonication with acetone and then by purging with nitrogen gas to remove any impurity. Structures for the linear transfer length method (L-TLMs) and a standard 2-point resistor were patterned using

FIGURE 1 | (a) Representative optical microscope image of part of a single TLM test structure. (b) Close up image of two 2-point resistor structures. (c) Four TLM test structures, B1–B4, belonging to a single block on the test chip. (d) Two 2-point resistor test structures -each with different MoS₂ channel widths for structures A1–A8 on the test chip.

multi-level optical lithography. For each level, a primer was coated on the pristine sample, followed by a negative photoresist and UV-exposure in a MA6 tool for patterning. A TMAH-based developer was used to develop the desired patterns. This was followed by dry etching of samples using SF₆/O₂ in an Oxford Plasma Etcher to define the MoS₂ channels. To define the metal contact pads, a Ti/Au metal stack (10/150 nm) was deposited using e-beam evaporation. A standard lift-off process, with acetone as the solvent, was utilized to complete the fabrication process. Some representative images of the fabricated devices are shown in Figure 1. Figure 1a,b represent the optical images of the as-fabricated L-TLMs structures and standard 2-point resistor, respectively. The yellow squares represent the metal pads used for probing during electrical measurements. Figure 1c shows one block of four repeat TLM structures on the chip B1 – B4. Figure 1d shows two repeat structures for eight different two-point resistors, A1–A8, each with a different track width (W). See Figures S1–S4. As all CVD-grown films were partially crystallized during growth. A single low temperature ALD-grown film was included in the sample set to demonstrate the ability of the laser process to crystallize an amorphous MoS₂ film. The detailed analysis of the crystallization of ALD grown MoS₂ [40] will be reported in a separate study.

2.2 | Laser Annealing Setup

An ultrashort pulsed laser system (Amplitude S-pulse) delivering pulses of duration 500 fs (FWHM) at the wavelength of 515 nm operated at pulse repetition frequency of 100 kHz was used for annealing of MoS₂ thin films. MoS₂ thin films and

fabricated devices were placed on a 3D computer-controlled machining stage (Aerotech Inc.) which moved the sample with sub-micrometre accuracy during the laser annealing process. The laser beam was directed through a combination of different mirrors and was focused on the samples with a telecentric F-Theta-Ronar lens (10 cm focal length, NA = 0.0014) via a Galvo scanning system (Hurricane II, Scanlab) which is coupled to the machining stage. An optical beam path for a camera was aligned with the laser beam, through the galvo scanning system, to enable targeting of specific sites. To keep the highest pulse to pulse stability and optimum beam shape, the laser was operated at the same nominal power and then attenuated using a combination of half-wave plate and polarizer. The spot diameter ($2\omega_0$) at $1/e^2$ of the laser Gaussian beam shape was calculated experimentally using Liu's method [41]. The samples were scanned with higher overlapping and different spots per area (SPA) as the speed of displacement of the beam varied from 100 – 250 mm s⁻¹. SPA was varied from 37 to 63 and energy per pulse changed from 0.15 to 0.45 μJ.

2.3 | Characterization

Raman spectroscopy was used as an in situ technique to observe the change in structure due to crystallization of MoS₂ before and after the laser annealing process. Raman spectra were acquired using a confocal Raman microscope (Renishaw InVia), equipped with an excitation Ar-ion laser source of 514.5 nm. For electrical measurements, the fabricated structures were electrically characterized at room temperature using an Agilent

BI500A semiconductor device analyzer integrated with a Cascade microtech probe station.

All cross-sectional STEM analysis was done using a probe corrected Thermo Fisher Scientific Spectra 300 operating at 300 kV. Interlayer spacing and film thickness values were measured using Velox software. Sample cross sections (lamellae) for cross-sectional TEM analysis were prepared employing a dual-beam focused ion beam (FIB) system (FEI Helios NanoLab 600i). Prior to FIB milling, protective layers were deposited over the area of interest. Initially, using electron beam-induced deposition, carbon layers ranging from 50 to 100 nm in thickness and platinum layers ranging from 50 to 150 nm were sequentially applied within the dual-beam FIB. Thereafter, a 3.5 μm thick platinum layer was deposited using ion beam-induced deposition. The prepared lamellae were then carefully lifted out and positioned onto a molybdenum sample grid (collected from Ted Pella, Inc, USA) in preparation for STEM analysis. To ensure electron transparency, the lamella was further thinned at 30 kV (0.28 nA), followed by a final polish at 5 kV (47 pA) to minimize FIB ion-beam induced damage.

Surface morphology was characterized using an atomic force microscope (AFM, Bruker Dimension Icon) operating in PeakForce Tapping mode, utilizing both ScanAsyst-Air and ScanAsyst Air-HPI probes with 2 nm nominal tip radius of curvature. PeakForce Tapping, similar to conventional tapping mode, involves periodic probe-sample contact, with interaction forces measured via cantilever deflection. A feedback loop maintains a constant peak force, enabling high-resolution imaging at low and controlled forces without the need for cantilever tuning. During scanning, the self-optimizing ScanAsyst algorithm automatically adjusted key imaging parameters, including setpoint, feedback gain, and scan rate, to ensure optimal performance. All AFM maps were processed and analyzed using Gwyddion, an open-source software that enabled image correction, statistical analysis, and grain boundary identification.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were carried out to study the change in the surface chemical composition upon laser annealing with different laser fluences. The results, presented in the support information, are presented for completeness. It should be noted there was a time delay of several weeks between the annealing step and the XPS measurements. The Kratos Axis Ultra instrument with monochromatic Al K α X-rays was used for the measurements.

3 | Results

3.1 | Optimization of Laser Scanning Parameters

Laser parameters such as fluence, scanning speed, and number of repeated scans are key parameters in material processing especially in laser annealing of MoS₂ thin films. Raman is a non-destructive optical technique and can be employed near to the laser annealing tool for in-situ quick structural and compositional analysis during laser processing. Raman analysis was performed to explore the optimum laser scanning parameters and their effects on thin film structure, such as changes in crystallinity,

phase, and defect generation in MoS₂ can be investigated before and after laser annealing process.

The SSPLA process is first introduced using a completely amorphous MoS₂ thin film grown by a different deposition process, low temperature ALD. While the current study is directed to investigate femtosecond laser annealing of CVD grown MoS₂ ultrathin films, Figure 2a shows the Raman spectra of as-deposited amorphous MoS₂ thin films grown by ALD at 150°C and subsequently the laser crystallized layer. The Raman spectrum of the amorphous MoS₂ exhibits a broad peak due to the disordered atomic arrangement, while the emergence of sharp in-plane (E_{2g}¹) and out-of-plane (A_{1g}) vibration modes confirmed the crystalline transition after the ultrashort pulsed laser annealing process. Figure 2b presents the Raman spectra of as-deposited CVD grown crystallized MoS₂ films before and after ultrashort laser annealing. The enhanced E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} peaks intensity and reduced full-width-at-half-maximum (FWHM) indicate an improvement in the overall crystallinity and reduced defects attained by laser processing. The peaks parameters (position, area, and width) were determined by fitting a Lorentzian function to the peaks in the Raman spectra. An investigation of the dependence of the Raman features on the laser parameters in Figure 2c–f is important to identify the scale of the acceptable process parameter space. The variation in the FWHM of E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} modes, difference in Raman shift of the peak (A_{1g}¹ – E_{2g}¹), and variation in A_{1g}¹/E_{2g}¹ peak intensity ratio with scanning speed and applied laser fluence are clearly observable. The FWHM of E_{2g}¹ starts to decrease at fluences greater than 4 mJ cm⁻² at a scanning speed of 100 – 200 mm s⁻¹, while the broadening of A_{1g} mode remains low and unchanged. The FWHM of E_{2g}¹ also decreases after 8 mJ cm⁻² with a similar decrease in the FWHM of the A_{1g} mode. Two optimum regions of fluence (4 – 6 mJ cm⁻²) and (8 – 10 mJ cm⁻²) at a laser scanning speed of between 100 and 200 mms⁻¹ are further considered in terms of the separation in wavenumbers of the peaks (A_{1g}¹ – E_{2g}¹) and the variation in the ratio of A_{1g}¹/E_{2g}¹ peak intensity. As the difference in the spectral positions of Raman peak A_{1g}¹ and E_{2g}¹ decreases, the MoS₂ layer is expected to become thinner [42]. The data presented in Figure 2e indicates that thinning is an effect observed at high fluences. The ratio of the A_{1g}¹/E_{2g}¹ intensities in Figure 2f varies above and below 2.0. Reports on ALD grown MoS₂ films suggest that this ratio is related to in-plane and out of plane growth [43]; the data presented for CVD grown materials does not clearly indicate a single preferential fluence range. In summary, it is proposed that the reduced FWHM values of both FWHM for E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} features should be considered simultaneously with the data presented for the ratio and separation of the E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} Raman features presented in Figure 2e,f.

3.2 | Site-Specific Device Annealing on Chip

The electrical characterization of the annealing process was performed using L-TLM test structures that were fabricated on the same device chip as the 2-point resistors (Figure 1c). This is important for consistency as the resistors and L-TLMs consist of the same MoS₂ thin-film fabricated on the same wafer.

A representative optical microscope image of the fabricated L-TLM is shown in Figure 1a. The purpose of that test structure

FIGURE 2 | (a) Raman spectra of amorphous ALD grown MoS₂ before and after ultra-short laser annealing showing characteristic peaks (E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g}) for the crystallized film. (b) Improvement in E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} peaks of CVD grown MoS₂, indicating enhanced crystallinity, after ultra-short laser annealing of partially crystalline materials. (c,d) Impact of laser fluence and scanning speed on different Raman spectral parameters of CVD grown MoS₂ thin films. (e,f) Variation in FWHM of E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} modes showing the dependence of difference in Raman shift of peaks (A_{1g} - E_{2g}¹), and variation in A_{1g}/E_{2g}¹ intensity ratio with scanning speed and applied laser fluence, respectively.

FIGURE 3 | (a) Current vs. voltage data for different spacings on L-TLM structures. (b) Data from which the contact resistance between the Ti/Au metal and the MoS₂ film is estimated. I - V characteristics showing the variation of current with MoS₂ channel width for (c) untreated and after laser annealing at different laser fluences: (d) 4.3 mJ cm⁻², (e) 7.2 mJ cm⁻², and (f) 10 mJ cm⁻². (g) Variation in resistance with reciprocal of width ($1/W$) for MoS₂ thin films before and after laser annealing at different fluences. The box-and-whisker plots represent resistance values before laser annealing while the triangular symbols indicate resistance after laser annealing at fluences from 4.3 to 11.5 mJ cm⁻².

is to extract the specific contact resistivity (ρ_c) in the standard way [44]. Representative electrical data of current vs. voltage as a function of electrode spacing are shown in Figure 3a. The extracted resistance vs. electrode spacing values is shown in Figure 3b. The intercept is an estimate of $2R_c$ or twice the contact resistance. The definition of the specific contact resistivity is $\rho_c = R_c \times A_c$, where the contact area A_c is defined as the overlap area between the metal contact pad and the MoS₂ thin film in the TLM structure. The contact resistance (R_c) in the 2-point resistor devices Figure 1b can be calculated from ρ_c/A_c using the known contact area of those devices. The total resistance (R_{TOTAL}) of the 2-point resistor geometries is calculated from the current vs. voltage plots like those presented in Figure 3c-f. The resistance for the MoS₂ channel is estimated from $R_{MOS2} = R_{TOTAL} - 2R_c$. An example calculation is presented for a typical device (“A8”) in Figure 1b where $A_c = 5.6 \times 10^3 \mu\text{m}^2$, the specific contact resistance from the L-TLM devices is $\rho_c = 8.1 \times 10^8 \Omega \mu\text{m}^2$, hence $R_c = \rho_c/A_c = 1.4$

$\times 10^5 \Omega$. In the 2-point resistance measurement is $R_{TOTAL} = 5.0 \times 10^9 \Omega$, with the conclusion that R_c is <1% of the R_{TOTAL} . This was concluded for all the 2-point resistor structures used in this study, regardless of MoS₂ channel width, W . Thus, when performing pulsed laser annealing (PLA) on the MoS₂ of the 2-point resistors, it is expected that R_{MOS2} is the dominant resistance of that device, making it easier to detect any changes as a function of PLA. If the R_c was a larger component of the overall resistance path, or an unknown, it would be difficult to extract subtle changes in R_{MOS2} .

The annealing process was applied to site-specific annealing on the 2-point resistor structure. Figure 3c illustrates the variation of current with the channel width before and after annealing at different laser fluences: (d) 4.3 mJ cm⁻², (e) 7.2 mJ cm⁻², and (f) 10 mJ cm⁻². The current increases with the channel width as expected, and higher laser fluence value further enhances current flow, leading to a reduction in resistance.

FIGURE 4 | Cross-sectional images obtained by STEM of the CVD-grown MoS₂ film at 400°C after device processing; (a) no-annealing, (b) 4.3 mJcm⁻², (c) 7.3 mJcm⁻² and (d) 10 mJcm⁻². Scale bars on both high-resolution upper and low-resolution lower images are 20nm.

Figure 3g demonstrates the variation in resistance of MoS₂ thin films with the reciprocal of width ($1/W$) of devices before and after the laser annealing at different fluences. The box-whisker represent resistance values before laser annealing, while the coloured triangular symbols indicate resistance after laser annealing at various laser fluences. As expected, the graph depicts the increase in resistance with decreasing width (W). The resistance values after laser annealing, at all investigated fluences, are consistently lower than the unannealed control sample (box plots). This suggesting that laser annealing successfully reduces resistance at all widths for the MoS₂ films. The results confirmed that decreases in resistance occurs with increasing laser fluence, showing an overall reduction of greater than 50% and by up to 75% following laser annealing. This significant reduction in resistance was observed at higher fluences (8.6 – 11.5 mJ cm⁻²).

3.3 | Cross sectional Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy

STEM was performed to analyse layer stacking, crystallinity and the onset of any melting at higher spatial resolution. The lamella for samples was prepared in the central MoS₂ regions of the 2-point resistor samples (Figure 1b). Cross-sectional STEM observations of post-processed CVD-grown MoS₂ films comprising devices without and with laser annealing are presented in Figure 4 a-d. The cross-sectional STEM image (Figure 4a) reveals a localized multi-layered structure that is mixed with an initial amorphous layer at the interface SiO₂ and then a crystalline layer at the top of the MoS₂ thin film. The thin film layer of MoS₂ varies from 3 to 6 nm as can be seen in Figure S5.1. The apparent variation in the MoS₂ thickness, observed in Figure 4a, arises from the presence of amorphous and crystalline phases (see Figure S5.1). The purpose of the laser annealing step is to improve the structural integrity of the MoS₂ film by converting the amorphous to a crystalline phase.

There are many cracked regions in the non-annealed sample that are not present in the laser annealed samples. After laser annealing there is also no indication of laser induced melting.

On close inspection and using through depth focusing STEM there is a 3D structure to the film as shown in Figures S5.2 and S1 video. There are also out of plane features in both non-annealed and annealed samples.

Figure 4b–d, show the annealed films at low and high magnification. There is an improvement in the structural integrity of the MoS₂ films after annealing, although we do not compare the same region before and after annealing. There are no amorphous regions detected, indicating that from the FIB samples analysed by STEM, the samples are fully crystalline. The inter layer separation in the crystalline structure was measured from the atomic resolution STEM (Figure S5.3) to be approximately 0.65 nm which is consistent with the calculated value of 0.65 nm shown in the 3D representation of the MoS₂ structure reported by Radisavljevic et al. [8]. The thicknesses of the annealed films across all fluences were found to be nearly similar, varying approximately from 5–7.5 nm (Figure S5.4). It is observed that, after the annealing treatment, the out-of-plane features above the main film persisted for all annealed samples. These unwanted features still exist in the films annealed at the high fluence but qualitatively their spatial density appears to be reduced.

In summary, cross sectional STEM show that ultrashort pulsed laser annealing improves the structural integrity of the films by specifically enhancing the crystallinity of the films by site specific pulsed laser annealing of devices.

3.4 | Atomic Force Microscopy

Figure 5 shows the topographic images of devices before and after laser annealing obtained by an AFM operating in tapping

FIGURE 5 | AFM topographic images of MoS₂ thin films before and after laser annealing of on-site devices at varying fluences (a) untreated (rms = 3.39 nm), (b) 4.3 mJ cm⁻² (rms = 3.34 nm), (c) 5.8 mJ cm⁻² (rms = 2.05 nm), (d) 7.2 mJ cm⁻² (rms = 3.03 nm), (e) 8.6 mJ cm⁻² (rms = 3.19 nm), (f) 10 mJ cm⁻² (rms = 3.39 nm), (g) 11.5 mJ cm⁻² (rms = 4.26 nm), and (h) 13 mJ cm⁻² (rms = 19.69 nm).

mode. Images are dominated by a complex relief structure consisting of compacted phases and local out of plane surface peaks represented by reddish and whiter colours, respectively. The topographic AFM images reveal significant morphological changes induced by ultrashort laser annealing of MoS₂ at different fluences.

The untreated sample 5(a) shows a relatively uniform surface with several out of plane structures. Under laser annealing, the MoS₂ film retains this general surface morphology up to a fluence of 11.5 mJ cm⁻². The only exception is at the laser fluence of 5.8 mJ cm⁻², where a noticeable smoother surface morphology is observed. The presence of raised features is noted throughout all measurements on annealed samples, Figure 5b–g. At the highest fluences of 11.5 and 13 mJcm⁻², Figure 5g,h, indicate a damaged structure. Figure 5g suggests the onset of damage as it shows the presence of raised (bright) and lower smooth (dark) structures. Damage to MoS₂ films is very evident in Figure 5h.

RMS roughness values are presented in the caption to Figure 5. The morphological damage at 13 mJ cm⁻² is confirmed by these measurements. Additional information extracted from grain boundary analysis of higher resolution AFM images is presented in Figure S6. The evolution of the grain boundaries with fluence is complex to interpret. The data indicates a grain structure where both large and small grains are present. There is no orientation to the grain structure which appears to be isotropic in nature.

SEM images presented in Figure S7, detects little change in the material up to 11.5 mJcm⁻². At that laser fluence we begin to see some imperfections in the material, although from the electrical data it is known this material is still highly conducting MoS₂ compared to other fluences. Above this fluence at 13 mJcm⁻² there is evidence of damage, visible at a relatively low zoom.

3.5 | EDX and XPS

While the paper primarily focuses on structure and electrical properties, some comments on the chemistry of the laser annealed layers is appropriate. The EDX spectra (Figure S8) acquired from the as grown and annealed film confirms the presence of Mo and S, consistent with previous reports [39]. XPS provides more detailed information on the chemical composition of the MoS₂ film before and after laser annealing. The XPS data (Figure S9) was recorded 2 months after the laser annealing step but is included for completeness. An untreated sample, and two regions with laser annealing at fluences of 5.8 and 11.5 mJ cm⁻² were analysed. In the untreated sample, the Mo⁶⁺ peaks were found to be more intense than the Mo⁴⁺ peaks, indicating significant surface oxidation. Post laser annealing, the intensity of Mo⁶⁺ peak further increased, whereas that of Mo⁴⁺ further decreased, suggesting enhanced oxidation of Mo on the surface. The peaks for SO_x became more intense on annealing, whereas those for S²⁻ decreased in intensity. This suggests that the loss of S from the surface may be an issue. A progressive increase was observed in the ratio of SO_x species compared to S²⁻ (from MoS₂) also occurs with increasing laser fluence. These results appear to challenge the claim that the laser annealed process is low temperature. They may also reveal something deeper, concerning the consequences of electron loss during ultrashort pulse laser exposure in ultra thin films. These results must be considered as preliminary, given that there was a delay between the laser treatment and the XPS measurements.

4 | Discussion

The significance of this work is that the electrical properties have been improved by modifying the structure of MoS₂ films in a low energy process. This low temperature approach is different to previous studies. A review of such studies shows MoS₂

modification is typically reported due to thermal treatments. Although not all of the following studies have presented electrical resistance data, some are worth considering in terms of MoS₂ alteration of physical properties.

In terms of crystallinity, Johari et al. noted that the crystallinity of 3 nm MoS₂ thin films improved significantly after annealing, as characterised by X-ray diffraction [45]. In that work the authors first annealed in O₂, followed by sulphurization, and then a high temperature annealing in an N₂ ambient. Recently, Chen et al. performed a study on monolayer (ML) MoS₂ using laser thermal anneal where they report this approach suppressed surface defects [46]. Furthermore, there are many works on the amorphous to crystalline transition, as opposed to the already-crystalline material modification. McConney et al. used magnetron sputtering from MoS₂ targets, to form amorphous films on polydimethylsiloxane substrates; these precursor films were subsequently laser annealed to form a few-layer crystalline TMDs [47]. In a similar vein, Becher et al. performed laser treatments on ALD films and characterised crystallisation and film morphology by Raman spectroscopy and SEM [48]. Meanwhile, Tonon et al. performed a similar study on crystallisation of sputtered MoS₂ and studied the material modification via Raman spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction, Rutherford backscattered spectroscopy (RBS), scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) and AFM [49]. Rai et al. also studied this amorphous to crystalline transition as MoS₂ material precursors were treated with a pulsed 532 nm laser to induce crystallisation in the material's semiconducting hexagonal phases [50]. Barvat et al. commented in their 2017 pulsed laser deposition (PLD) work that post growth annealing could be one of the ways to improve the crystalline quality of the films [51]. Sirota et al. crystallised their MoS₂ material, and demonstrated electrical conductivity on flexible substrates [52]. Finally, Kaindl et al. found that room temperature physical vapour deposition (PVD) MoS₂ films are amorphous, but readily degrade during laser-induced annealing in an ambient atmosphere [53]. It is noteworthy that the PVD films deposited at 400 °C are nanocrystalline initially which is like the CVD grown materials used in this study.

The selection of a low fluence ultrashort laser pulse to enable a low temperature site-specific PLA process is therefore different. In laser material interactions, the laser has the potential to deliver a precise, localized transfer of energy to the material allowing precise material modification. The potential of ultrashort laser technology is because of its extremely short pulse durations. This feature offers a smaller heat affected zone (HAZ) compared to CW and long pulse lasers [54]. Femtosecond (fs) lasers deliver energy on time scales of less than 10⁻¹² seconds, which is shorter than the electron phonon relaxation time of most metallic and semiconducting materials where relaxation occurs on the order of several picoseconds. Therefore, the laser energy transfer during such a short interval can enable a novel non-thermal response in the material.

This unique two temperature interaction enables a unique response which entails: Athermal excitation of electrons in MoS₂ film occurs near to the surface. The thermalisation of excited electrons within femtoseconds to establish an elevated electron temperature while the lattice temperature remains cold or unaffected. Carefully controlling peak fluence provided by the

femtosecond laser manages the maximum electron temperature attained and therefore reduces the temperature difference with the lattice which ultimately causes this period of non-equilibrium to lengthen. In addition, careful control of the incident micro-Joule pulse ultimately limits the temperature the lattice attains after thermalisation.

The diffusive mechanism by which the structure of MoS₂ films is annealed in this low temperature regime is not clear. Energising the electronic subsystem can be considered as a temporary lowering of the cohesive forces particularly if electrons are either photoelectrically or thermoelectrically ejected from the film. While this is a matter of speculation, it is reasonable given the proximity of the surface to all regions where the laser energy is absorbed in an ultrathin film. Moreover, the presence of out of plane features may contribute to this temporary electron emission. In terms of diffusion, this temporary modification can be considered to lower the activation energy associated with atomic diffusion resulting in a non-thermal solid state anneal.

The effects of ultra-short laser annealing on the properties of CVD prepared MoS₂ thin films-based devices was systematically investigated in this study using multiple characterization techniques. The applied laser fluence was optimised with a Raman analysis tool to identify the laser parameters for SSPLA. Raman spectroscopy showed a decrease in FWHM of the characteristic E_{2g}¹ and A_{1g} modes, confirming enhancement in the phonon lifetime, crystalline quality, and reduction in structural disorder. The Raman maps presented in Figure 2 indicate that a reasonable process window for laser fluence and scan speed may be attained which is advantageous for accommodating variations obtained in industrial processing.

Demonstration of the site-specific application of the pulsed laser annealing process followed on real devices. The as-received CVD material had an inherent variability in it. This is observed in Figure 3b. To address this variability, several devices were considered. Technically this was realised using a through the lens viewing arrangement on the laser system. In terms of processing, it required overlapped pulses to ensure uniform exposure. The results presented in Figure 3 confirm some success in reducing the resistance of the MoS₂ channels. Further optimisation could lead to greater reduction in resistances. This optimisation could be based on controlling the environment or by combining the laser annealing process with real time measurements of resistance, as is typical in industrial processing of components on semiconductor wafers.

While our hypothesis is that periodic structures reduce the scattering of carriers that give rise to resistance it is useful to reflect that resistance arises due to two parameters. Resistance in a homogeneously thick and homogeneously doped semiconductor thin film can be defined as

$$R = \frac{1}{q \cdot \mu \cdot n \cdot x} \quad (1)$$

where R is resistance, q is electronic charge, n is carrier concentration, μ is carrier mobility, and x is semiconductor layer thickness. While q is considered fixed, variations in R can only come from changes in x , μ or n . STEM results confirm an effective

increase in x , the thickness of the crystalline layer through which conduction proceeds. Increased mobility and/or increased carrier concentration would result in reduced R , as seen from the PLA results attained for treated MoS₂ devices.

Considering factors that could change μ , one must consider scattering that occurs as charge flows through the material; specifically surface scattering, ionised charge scattering, and phonon scattering which occurs with increasing temperature. Scattering events can be influenced by the crystal quality of the material, with defects, and grain boundaries hampering the flow of current. Furthermore, surface scattering arises due to physical structural imperfections of the semiconductor crystal along its boundaries. Hence, with improved crystal quality observed in STEM, one could expect reduced carrier scattering, a better μ , and reduced resistance as a result. Changes in the carrier concentration, n , is more difficult to interpret. Crystalline structure creates a band structure which for MoS₂ can be either metallic or semiconducting depending on its phase. As it was not possible to determine the phase of the annealed material in this study, we are unable to precisely comment how the parameter, n , was impacted. However, for the sake of discussion, we consider a semiconducting phase. We will also focus on electrons in the conduction band, but the discussion is equivalent for holes in the valence band. Increased carrier concentrations can come from several factors including changes in, for example, density of states and probability of occupation, the bandgap and the Fermi-Dirac distribution function. We assume here that the impurity doping in the material is constant, as the materials under study in this work are non-intentionally doped. The distribution function for electron energy, known as the Fermi-Dirac distribution function, is given by

$$f(E) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp\left(\frac{E-E_f}{kT}\right)} \quad (2)$$

where E_f is the Fermi level, k is the Boltzmann constant, and T is temperature. The distribution of electrons then can be derived from $f(E)$ and the density of allowed states, $g(E)$, by integrating over the conduction band:

$$n = \int_{E_c}^{\infty} f(E) \cdot g(E) \cdot dE \quad (3)$$

The carrier concentration in the conduction band, these equations can be simplified to:

$$n = N_c \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{(E_c - E_f)}{kT}\right) \quad (4)$$

with E_c being the conduction band energy, and N_c is the donor concentration. The consequence of this is, if the bandgap is reduced, then $E_c - E_f$ is reduced, and then n increases, assuming all other factors remain the same. If the stoichiometry of the MoS₂ is changed to make it, say, more metallic (Mo) the bandgap would change, and would potentially correspond to a reduction of S observed in the XPS analysis.

A key approach is that differences in the contact resistance are less relevant to this study, as in our site-specific PLA

approach, the contact areas were intentionally left untreated. This is different to previous reports. Kwon et al. observed a reduced contact resistance in monolayer MoS₂ devices resulting from a decrease of Schottky barrier width at the MoS₂-metal junction [55]. Kwon et al. also demonstrated that selectively laser annealed source/drain electrodes can produce a Schottky to Ohmic transition [56]. Xie et al. studied the annealing effects on sulphur vacancies and electronic transport of MoS₂ films grown by pulsed-laser deposition, where it was stated, that due to the elimination of Mo oxide, the Fermi level was shifted, resulting in a Schottky contact instead of an Ohmic contact [57]. Recently, Wani et al. used pulsed laser anneal to thermally drive Ag atoms into single layer MoS₂, using Ag filaments to laterally contact with the edge of the device structure [58]. Similarly, Kwon et al. observed improved performance by laser annealing in thin-film transistors, based on multi-layer MoS₂ and indium zinc oxide (IZO) electrodes which was attributed to the reduction of the contact resistance between MoS₂ and IZO [59].

STEM data (Figure 4a-d; Figures S5.1-S5.4) confirmed that post processed CVD MoS₂ films grown at 400°C remains partly crystalline. The crystallinity is significantly increased during ultrashort pulsed laser annealing (Figure 4). While the STEM results indicate that there may be some thinning of MoS₂ further studies are required to develop a robust comparison between this technique and Raman results.

The AFM data (Figure 5) confirms the presence of many out of plane features through all fluences used in this study. It is noteworthy that this AFM data is recorded at relatively low resolution. A more accurate picture could be obtained using slower scan rates at higher resolution in future. The analysed AFM data provides a sense of the distribution of lateral grain sizes (Figure S6). The presence of non-aligned isotropic grain boundaries is encouraging. The enhancement in grain size which occurred at high fluences suggest that there is some coalescence of grains which leads to an improvement film continuity after laser annealing.

XPS revealed notable reduction in sulphur contents after annealing suggesting generation of sulphur vacancies (Figure S9), particularly at high fluence. The results are also contrary to what was expected for non-thermal ultrashort laser material interactions. This apparent contradiction can only be resolved experimentally by operating at low fluence, or by applying an ultrashort pulse laser process in a controlled sulphur rich environment, or by developing a method to estimate the temperature of the film during laser processing. The use of simulation tools to estimate the temperature is complicated for MoS₂, and materials other than metals in general, due to the complexity of considering inter-band and intra-band absorption and relaxation pathways in semiconductors.

5 | Conclusion

Ultrashort laser pulses were successfully applied to directly anneal MoS₂ devices using a site-specific pulsed laser annealing process (SSPLA) performed in ambient air. High spatial pulse overlapping, was used to improve the electrical and structural properties of MoS₂ in devices without causing thermal damage.

The SSPLA process was confirmed by Raman, STEM, and AFM to improve the degree of crystallization of partially crystallized films. The SSPLA process was able to consistently improve the electrical properties of MoS₂ tracks with high precision. Preliminary XPS showed that oxidation occurs at higher fluence while low to moderate fluence ranges could offer greater retention or sulphur. The results indicate that the proposed SSPLA process could be used to tune resistive elements and improve the contact resistance directly on TFT devices. These thin films are not intentionally doped and so the resistance of the material remains high; doping and device scaling will both reduce resistance. The results also demonstrate the potential for SSPLA to be used in scalable 2D thin film processing of complex structures in future semiconducting technologies. An intriguing future challenge would be to investigate if the site-specific ultrashort pulsed laser annealing process would be applicable to one- or two-layer MoS₂ materials.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

All data will be made available from the UCC or University of Galway Repository.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section.

Supporting File: sml172568-sup-0001-SuppMat.docx.